

APPLICATION OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN
MOTHER TONGUE AND LITERATURE LESSONS IN GENERAL
SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation: *This article discusses the use of innovative technologies in mother tongue and literature classes in general secondary schools, the use of interactive methods, encourages students to think creatively, to be proactive, to work together, to express ideas fluently.*

Keywords: *native language, literature, lessons, innovative technology, method, game distance learning, pronunciation, speaking skills, modern technical means, verification methods, language meanings.*

It is important to note that the introduction of non-traditional lessons in the lessons "Mother tongue and literature" and their integration into the content of education, finding new ways of teaching will create the basis for meeting the requirements of state educational standards. The role of the lessons "Mother tongue and literature" in the comprehensive development of the human personality, instilling in the younger generation a sense of respect for universal and national values, a sense of pride in the national language, the traditions of their people is invaluable. .

At the present time, the pedagogue of the XXI century is required not only to provide theoretical knowledge, but also to convey this knowledge to students in more effective ways, to create a basis for easy, accurate and rapid assimilation of knowledge, to form logical thinking, creativity and fluency in students. . Of course, such tasks are carried out through innovative technologies, various interactive games. So, now the teacher is required to move from a traditional lesson to a non-traditional lesson:

The main directions of the non-traditional lesson:

a) teaching students to think independently;

- b) focus the student's attention on one point;
- d) to give students a clear idea of the basics of science, their achievements;
- e) applying the acquired knowledge in practice and teaching it to others, etc.

It is hard to imagine non-traditional lessons without interactive methods and games. After all, these are the core of the lesson. For example, "Brainstorming", "Intelligence", "Zigzag", "Interactive", "Game lesson", "Debate lesson", "Travel lesson", "Competition" to easily bring a complex topic to the minds of students. It is especially important to use in the educational process such as "lesson", "FSMU", "Fish skeleton", "Wheel".

The interactive methods used in the lessons help students to develop a sense of love for their mother tongue and country, to raise them to the level of perfect literacy, to achieve logical, clear and complete speech. implies

The use of such interactive methods and games throughout the lesson is primarily related to the skill of the educator. The reason is that the methods should be prepared the day before the lesson, the necessary visual aids, handouts, short question-and-answer and tests, the formation of assessment criteria, as well as the motivation and punishment of learners. Each method requires the teacher to select and prepare for easy and difficult types, taking into account the age of the students, their interests, the proportion of the number of boys and girls, whether the learning process is fast or relatively slow, their abilities and strengths. are given.

It is also important to have action games in the 45-minute session. Because it is also the teacher's job not to tire the children and to rest their brains and muscles through wisely chosen 3-4 minute movement games. In the course of the lessons, great attention should be paid to the forms of oratory, conversation, storytelling, independent work, written work, the development of socio-political knowledge through the connection with the present, the reliance on independent thought.

Another aspect to consider is the use of computer technology in native language and literature classes. To do this, the teacher must first provide the classroom with the necessary equipment, and then create presentations, videos, short films, pictures and samples of creativity on the topic, or selectively download quality ones from websites.

The main reason for this is that they help to expand the creativity and worldview of students, develop visual learning and of course make the learning process more interesting and quality. This method makes it easier to understand grammatically complex topics, develops students' ability to compose independent text from simple sentences to small texts, visualizes and better remembers the life and work of literary figures, and enjoys their work on screen. is characterized by the fact that it helps to

Especially in the context of the current global coronavirus pandemic, another opportunity for teachers is the creation of audio and video lessons for distance learning. In addition to the lessons, additional lessons created by favorite teachers who are familiar to the students can give them strength, motivation, and of course, additional knowledge.

One of the great and responsible tasks set by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the "National Training Program" for teachers, scientists and all specialists in the education system organization of the educational process on the basis of advanced modern pedagogical technologies. To this end, it is no coincidence that special attention is paid to the acquisition of languages by students.

After all, in order to operate successfully in modern conditions, each young person is required to be fluent in several languages, fluent in at least two, but four world languages, except Uzbek (state). To achieve this, it is necessary to develop and implement a program of activities aimed at updating the content of education, improving existing curricula and textbooks, and most importantly - the creation of new educational complexes, all components of which are essentially and methodologically common.

In recent years, the world education system has paid great attention to the implementation of independent methods of language acquisition in accordance with modern requirements. In particular, in our country, every teacher of language and literature focuses on teaching their lessons on the basis of new pedagogical technologies.

In order to effectively organize mother tongue lessons in schools, teachers should pay attention to the following aspects:

1. Organize the lesson in groups of 8-12, 15-20 people.
2. Use of modern technical means (video-recorder, computer and other audiovisual equipment) in teaching.
3. Independent use of language textbooks, as well as textbooks, manuals, methodological manuals, methodological guidelines on topics and developments in language teaching.
4. To pay attention to the theoretical study of the language, the formation of new speaking skills in the organization of training sessions.

It is also important to develop the ability to pronounce correctly and to increase vocabulary on a regular basis in mother tongue teaching. In this case, the use of technical means - video and audio recorders gives good results.

Independent work (on the text) in the study of the mother tongue is one of the most important conditions for ensuring the quality of education, by improving the

ability of students to express themselves independently and freely in the language they are learning determined. In independent work it is advisable to carry out practical work (exercises on the topic) on the identified topic, as well as to conduct research on a specific topic.

Practice plays an important role for the applied sciences. Native language science is also one of the applied sciences. Any practical conclusions must be convincing, highly scientific, that is, thorough and well-founded. The scientific level of the methodological recommendations, the high level of theoretical validation also depends on the accuracy of the verification methods.

There are 2 types of verification methods:

1. Methods of theoretical examination.

2. Empirical method (experience-based method). This method is used for the following purposes:

a) this method is the study of teachers' work experience, selection, generalization, evaluation and dissemination of innovations, determination of the level of activity of teachers and students;

b) purposeful monitoring of the teaching process of students (lesson, part of it, checking students' answers, stories, written work), checking the activities of teachers and students through a survey;

In particular, it is necessary to reorganize the teaching of the principles of understanding the meanings of language (lexical, grammatical, morphemic, syntactic meanings) in the native language classes of secondary schools. Understanding a word, a morpheme, a phrase, a sentence means determining the connection between certain events in an being.

The condition for adhering to the principle of understanding the meanings of language is the teaching of all aspects of language, all the disciplines of language (grammar, lexicon, phonetics, spelling, methodology) in an interconnected way. For example, morphology can be taught and mastered only on the basis of syntax.

The study of syntax is based on morphology, spelling is based on phonetics, grammar is based on word formation, and so on. Morphemic analysis of a word helps to understand its meaning. All aspects of language are interconnected and this must be taken into account in teaching

In short, in-depth mastery of the science of mother tongue and literature can be more thorough, easy, and quick through the judicious use of interactive methods, games, and computer technology used by the modern educator.

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